

Super Accelerated Motion in Rindler Spacetime

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Abstract: In the general relativity theory, we discover formulas that the super accelerated matter moves with the acceleration a_0 about Rindler space-time. We can represent the super accelerated motion about coordinates x, ct, ξ^0 . PACS Number:04,04.90.+e

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the general relativity theory, we discover formulas that the super accelerated matter moves with the acceleration a_0 about Rindler space-time.

At first, Rindler coordinate is

$$ct = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$x = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0} \quad (2)$$

$$y = \xi^2, Z = \xi^3 \quad (3)$$

In Eq (1),

$$\xi^1 + \frac{c^2}{a_0} = \frac{ct}{\sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)} \quad (4)$$

If we insert Eq(4) in Eq(2),

$$x = ct \coth\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0} \quad (5)$$

If we insert Eq(5) in Eq(2),

$$ct \coth\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \quad (6)$$

Hence, the result is

$$\xi^1 = \frac{ct}{\sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)} - \frac{c^2}{a_0} \quad (7)$$

2. THE SUPER ACCELERATED MOTION ABOUT AN UNIFORMLY ACCELERATED FRAME

$$d\tau^2 = (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})^2 (d\xi^0)^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} [(d\xi^1)^2 + (d\xi^2)^2 + (d\xi^3)^2] \tag{8}$$

Hence, if the super accelerated matter moves with the acceleration a_0' about an uniformly accelerated frame,

$$a_0' = \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left[\frac{\left(\frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0}\right)}{\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0}\right)^2 / c^2}} \right] \tag{9}$$

If we compute,

$$(a_0' \xi^0)^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0}\right)^2}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0}\right)^2 / c^2} \tag{10}$$

Then,

$$\left(\frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0}\right)^2 = (a_0' \xi^0)^2 \left[\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0}\right)^2 / c^2 \right] \tag{11}$$

If we compute about $\frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0}$,

$$\frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} = \frac{a_0' \xi^0 \left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{(a_0' \xi^0)^2}{c^2}}} \tag{12}$$

In Eq(12), if we multiply $\frac{d\xi^0}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)}$,

$$\frac{d\xi^1}{1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}} = \frac{a_0' \xi^0 d\xi^0}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{(a_0' \xi^0)^2}{c^2}}} \tag{13}$$

If we integrate Eq(13),

$$\frac{c^2}{a_0} \ln \left| 1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2} \right| = \frac{c^2}{a_0} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{(a_0' \xi^0)^2}{c^2}} - 1 \right) \tag{14}$$

Hence, if we compute about the coordinate ξ^1 , we can represent the super accelerated motion by

Rindler coordinates ξ^1, ξ^0 .

$$\xi^1 = \frac{c^2}{a_0} \left[\exp \frac{a_0'}{a_0} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{(a_0' \xi^0)^2}{c^2}} - 1 \right) - 1 \right] \tag{15}$$

If we insert Eq(7) in Eq(15),

$$\xi^1 = \frac{c^2}{a_0} \left[\exp \frac{a_0}{a_0'} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{(a_0' \xi^0)^2}{c^2}} - 1 \right) - 1 \right] = \frac{ct}{\sinh \left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c} \right)} - \frac{c^2}{a_0} \quad (16)$$

Hence, we can represent the super accelerated motion about coordinates ct, ξ^0 .

$$ct = \frac{c^2}{a_0} \exp \frac{a_0}{a_0'} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{(a_0' \xi^0)^2}{c^2}} - 1 \right) \sinh \left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c} \right) \quad (17)$$

If we insert Eq(17) in Eq(5), we can represent the super accelerated motion about coordinates x, ξ^0 .

$$x = ct \coth \left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c} \right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0} = \frac{c^2}{a_0} \exp \frac{a_0}{a_0'} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{(a_0' \xi^0)^2}{c^2}} - 1 \right) \cosh \left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c} \right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0} \quad (18)$$

3. CONCLUSION

In the general relativity theory, we discover formulas that the super accelerated matter moves with the acceleration in an uniformly accelerated frame.

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